

RESILIENCE OF NURSING STUDENTS IN ONLINE LEARNING MODALITY

DOI

Gaudymer A. Lopez

Faculty, University of the East Ramon Magsaysay

<https://orcid.org/0009-0006-1411-6508>

Ma. Leni C. Francisco, Ph.D

Program Head, STI West Negros University, Bacolod City Philippines

<https://orcid.org/0009-0007-2401-1897>

Abstract:

Understanding student resilience has become increasingly important with the shift to online learning due to the COVID-19 pandemic. This study determined the resilience levels in online learning modality nursing students in an online learning environment at a private, non-sectarian academic institution in Dasmariñas City, Cavite, Philippines, during the 2022-2023 academic year to inform the development of a wellness plan. One hundred thirty-eight (138) Level III and IV BS Nursing students were surveyed. The study used a descriptive research design and a researcher-made survey questionnaire. In the analysis of the results of the study, the researcher used descriptive and comparative procedures. For the statistical tools, frequency, percentage, mean, and Mann-Whitney U test were used. The level of resilience of nursing students in online learning modality according to self-awareness, mindfulness and positive relationship was "high." Also results shows no significant difference in the level of resilience of nursing students in online learning modality in self-awareness, mindfulness, and positive relationship when grouped and compared according to age, year level, and average family monthly income. Result of this study calls for psychology education to integrate resilience-building strategies into the curriculum, for psychological practice to incorporate evidence-based resilience interventions into their clinical work, for psychological institutions to prioritize the well-being of students, faculty, and staff, and for psychological research to continue exploring the factors contributing to resilience across diverse populations and contexts to inform evidence-based interventions and practices.

Keywords: Resilience, nursing students, online learning, self-awareness, mindfulness, positive relationship

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

The global spread of the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19), caused by the novel SARS-CoV-2, has led to unprecedented consequences for millions worldwide. As highlighted in Munir et al.'s (2021) study, the pandemic has forced students into prolonged indoor settings, adapting to the new normal of remote learning from home, thereby highlighting the pivotal role of online education. This shift has profoundly affected students' daily lives, elevating the significance of online teaching and learning across both developed (Dost et al., 2020) and developing nations (Dashtestani, 2020).

Besides the devastating health consequences, the pandemic affects students' physical and mental well-being (Zolotov et al., 2020). A Barrett (2022) review highlighted the substantial impact of the pandemic on nursing students, but what does the evidence tell us about why this group has been hit so hard? Meanwhile, according to Rizqi (2017), resilience is the ability to "bounce back" after a traumatic experience. It is being able to rise above a very stressful and compromising situation. It is the ability to overcome stress and adapt to challenges. Resilience is thought of as a dynamic resting not only on the attributes of an individual but also on the environmental and social factors intermingled in a person's life. The numerous facets of resilience, including self-awareness, mindfulness, and strong relationships, were listed by Cagayan (2021). She determined that the level of self-awareness was very high. She also discovered that the respondents had high interpersonal and mindfulness abilities. Based on the study's findings, the researcher, as a faculty member in the school of nursing, was motivated to study this topic based on students' experiences.

This study focused mainly on the level of resilience of nursing students in the online learning modality of a selected nursing school in terms of self-awareness, mindfulness, and positive relationships. As the researcher observed, the pandemic has taken its toll on the mental health and resilience of the students. The shift in learning modality during this pandemic and as a mental health advocate motivates the researcher to study students' resiliency in an

online learning modality, which served as the basis for a wellness plan. The results of this study and the proposed wellness plan will be significant for the nursing students and the parents, school administrators, and faculty members.

Current State of Knowledge

Staneva et al. (2022) found that psychological distress affects all age groups, but younger adults tend to experience it more significantly. Other things being equal, the COVID-19 pandemic added to the psychological distress of young females and males (aged 16–25) relative to their pre-pandemic. In addition, young men, in particular, struggle more. Meanwhile, according to Mash'al et. Al (2020), the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic has forced schools and universities worldwide to switch their face-to-face teaching-learning activities to online, distance, or remote learning.

According to an article in Times Higher Education (2022), while most universities worldwide incorporate some form of online education, transitioning all programs to online platforms presents challenges. While larger institutions already have robust online systems, smaller universities may require assistance to meet the demand. Collaboration between university course developers and IT departments is crucial to ensure adequate online program support. As online learning becomes increasingly essential, universities must prioritize the safety of students and staff on campus. Suryaman et al. (2020) examined the dynamics of home-based learning during the pandemic. They identified several barriers in this setting, including limited technological proficiency; high costs associated with internet access, and reduced opportunities for student interaction and socialization. There are three areas of concern regarding nursing students' resilience in this study: self-awareness, mindfulness, and positive relationships.

In addition, according to Antonini et al. (2021), practicing mindfulness during challenging events can enhance resilience, which is crucial for effectively managing adversity. Encouraging mindfulness among younger individuals may be beneficial for fostering protective factors. From a practical perspective, engaging in physical activity or mindfulness practices can help individuals develop resilience against potentially traumatic situations like a pandemic. Therefore, promoting health programs incorporating mindfulness and physical activity could be essential in addressing the potentially traumatic impacts of a pandemic. Moreover, positive relationships refer to the good relationships people build with others that not only relate to depressive symptoms but are also associated with resilience, according to Lee et al. (2021).

Furthermore, Tanji F. et al. (2021) found that resilience enables medical science students, particularly nursing students, to concentrate intently on their studies despite the increased likelihood of academic stress. They added that there was a significant association between the vitality of resilience components and academic performance among nursing students. Thus, they suggested that an approach that develops resilience is necessary for the educational success of nursing students. It has further taken higher education in general into unprecedented times, according to Head et al. (2022). The swift shift from in-person to online teaching and learning posed significant challenges for students, educators, and administrators. Medical and nursing education faced an incredibly daunting task in determining effective methods to teach healthcare provision, which traditionally relies on in-person, hands-on approaches in an online format.

Moreover, Miranda et al. (2020), cited that resilience characterizes the Filipino people during hardship. Filipinos in Filipino culture and on social media often depict themselves as a community that smiles in the face of adversity. This portrayal contributes to a national identity of strength, where humor and smiles are seen as valuable assets. The outbreak of Corona Virus Disease-2019 (COVID-19), according to Clemen et al. (2021), has compelled higher education institutions (HEIs) all over the world to adopt electronic learning (e-learning), the delivery of learning using digital resources. As e-learning expands, HEIs are more curious to learn whether students are prepared to use new technologies, adjust to the new learning environment, and engage in self-directed learning. However, because of the financial capacities of the students and professors, HEIs in less economically developed nations like the Philippines face difficulties in making the switch to e-learning. He added that Filipino higher education students must prepare for e-learning during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Theoretical Underpinnings

The study was anchored on Dr. Norman Garmezy's Resilience Theory (1991). The word resilience was first used by Dr. Norman Garmezy, a clinical psychologist often noted as a founder of research in resilience. His research work was about stress, competence, and childhood development.

This study's primary focus was to determine how and what factors determine resiliency for nursing students. Students experienced different challenges during this pandemic and may exhibit resiliency characteristics differently than others. Resilient students adjust to adversities quicker and more substantially than others and use their experiences to develop new skills and gain more confidence. These adversities could help students become more aware of how their actions must be adjusted to accommodate difficult situations.

In this time of the pandemic, Garmezy (1991) defines resilience as "not During the pandemic, Garmezy (1991) defined resilience not as immunity to stress, but as the ability to recover and sustain adaptive behavior after an initial setback or incapacity caused by a stressful event. According to Dr. Garmezy, resilience involves "functional adequacy," which refers to maintaining competent functioning despite emotional challenges, serving as a hallmark of resilient behavior under stress. Concerning the study, amidst the pandemic and changes in the learning modalities, the students maintain an adequate function in their academic, personal, and interpersonal aspects.

Objectives

This study aimed to determine the level of resilience of nursing students in online learning modality in a private, non-sectarian, coeducational academic institution of Nursing in Dasmarinas City, Cavite, Philippines, during the academic year 2022- 2023 as the basis for a wellness plan. This study sought to answer the following questions: 1) the nursing students' resilience level in online learning modality according to the area of self-awareness, mindfulness and positive relationship; 2) the nursing students' resilience level in online learning modality when grouped according to the abovementioned variables; and 3) the significant difference in nursing students' resilience level in online learning modality when grouped and compared according to the abovementioned variables.

Methodology

This section presents the discussion of the research methodology used, the subjects and respondents of the study, the research instruments used, the validity and reliability of the instruments, the procedure for data gathering, and the statistical tools and procedure for data analysis.

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive research design to determine the level of resilience of nursing students in an online learning modality in one of the private, non-sectarian, coeducational academic institutions of nursing at Dasmarinas City, Cavite, Philippines, during the academic year 2022-23. Descriptive design was used to describe the characteristics of the population or phenomenon being studied. It answered questions about how, when, and why the characteristics occurred. It is a study that depicts the participants accurately. More simply, descriptive research is all about describing people who participate in the study, and it can be done using observation, case study, or survey (Kowalczyk, 2016). Meanwhile, it was appropriate for this study because it provided important information about the present status of the study. This method was applied to this study because of the present condition of learners adjusting to an online learning modality.

Study Respondents

The study's respondents were 138 student nurses from 3rd and 4th Year level students from a total population of 216. They were from the private, non-sectarian, coeducational academic institution of nursing at Dasmarinas City, Cavite, Philippines, during the academic year 2022-2023 and with the use of purposive sampling in the selection of respondents. According to Arikunto (2010), purposive sampling is selecting a sample by taking a subject that is not based on the level or area. However, it is taken based on the specific purpose.

Instruments

In this study, the researcher-made questionnaire was utilized. It was subjected to validity (4.89-excellent) and reliability (0.915-excellent). All of them were interpreted as worthy and good; respectively. The questionnaire was divided into 2 parts wherein part 1 focused on the basic information sheet, including the respondents' age, year level, and average family monthly income. Part 2 was the student's resiliency in online learning: self-awareness, mindfulness, and positive relationships. The instrument had 20 items and was divided into four areas of concern. Each part of the questionnaire required the participants to read the items and mark the preferred option, except for the first part related to their personal information. The respondents responded either (5) always, (4) often, (3) sometimes, (2) rarely, (1) almost never.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher requested permission through written communication from the Dean of the School or College, requesting that the researcher distribute the questionnaires to the target respondents. After granting the permission, the researcher conducted the survey questionnaire for each respondent. The purpose of the study was adequately explained to respondents by the researcher. This study was completed using quantitative methods and a researcher-made online survey.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No.1 used a descriptive-analytical scheme and mean to determine the nursing student’s resiliency level in online learning.

Objective No.2 also used a descriptive-analytical scheme and mean to determine nursing students’ resiliency level in online learning modalities when grouped according to the variables.

Objective No. 3 used a comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U test to determine whether there is a significant difference in the level of nursing students’ resiliency in online learning modalities when grouped and compared according to the abovementioned variables.

Ethical Consideration

Issues considered in establishing the validity and reliability of the data, analysis, and findings. Ethical considerations were applied during the study. The name of the school and the respondents were not revealed in this study, while the purpose of this study was clearly and wholly discussed to them as the researcher's obligation. The data gathered from the survey, whether in writing as they answered the questionnaire or through Google Forms, were used only for the study. Consequently, the researcher did not inject personal opinions and judgment regarding the result of the study, and all the data and information gathered were kept confidential.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data gathered to carry out the objectives of this study. All these were made possible by following certain appropriate procedures so as to give the exact data and solution to each specific problem.

Table 1
Level of Resilience of Nursing Students in Online Learning Modalities on Self-Awareness

Area	Mean	Interpretation
A. Self-Awareness		
<i>As a student, I am.</i>		
1. aware of the different remote teaching modalities implemented by CHED.	4.25	High Level
2. aware of the dos and don'ts of implementing online learning modality during the pandemic.	4.54	Very High Level
3. aware of the importance of using ICT in online learning and school paperwork.	4.67	Very High Level
4. aware of the need for knowledge for accurate and updated learning areas and content in the learning platforms.	4.68	Very High Level
5. aware of the emotional components of the online learning modality.	4.38	High Level
6. aware of the importance of taking care of my physical, emotional, and mental health.	4.41	High Level
7. aware of the strengths of the online learning modality.	4.27	High Level
8. aware of the weaknesses and limitations of the online learning modality.	4.65	Very High Level
9. aware of my mindset to meet goals and needs and face challenges.	4.42	High Level
10. aware to maintain or sustain positive relationships in a challenging situation.	4.29	High Level
Overall Mean	4.46	High Level

Interpreting the area of self-awareness, as presented in Table 1, the overall mean score was 4.46, interpreted as "high level." the respondents obtained the highest mean score of 4.68 on item No. 4, which states "aware of the need of knowledge for accurate and updated learning areas and content in the learning platforms" interpreted as "very high level." Meanwhile, the lowest mean of 4.25 was on item No. 1, which states awareness of CHED's different remote teaching modalities—interpreted as "high level."

This implies that several respondents are unaware of the different teaching modalities the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) implemented. As allowed by CHED, there are various remote teaching modalities that schools, colleges, universities, faculties, students, and stakeholders should be aware of. Online learning is one example. The so-called "digital divide" affects Filipino learners regarding technology access and remote teaching modalities like online learning.

The research conducted by Joaquin, Biana, and Dacela (2020) highlights significant socio-economic challenges related to online learning in a developing country like the Philippines. Students in remote areas often lack basic

infrastructure such as roads and electricity, making access to computers and the internet unattainable. Additionally, due to the current internet infrastructure, even students in urban areas may experience limited internet access, creating a "digital divide" between those with access and those without. Consequently, this divide restricts students' awareness of various teaching modalities during the pandemic.

Table 2
Level of Resilience of Nursing Students in Online Learning Modalities on Mindfulness

Area	Mean	Interpretation
B. Mindfulness		
<i>As a student, I am mindful...</i>		
1. that my professor/faculty member introduces the concepts, pedagogy, technology, strategies, and instructional designs in an online learning modality	4.27	High Level
2. of online modules or learning materials, such as YouTube, Google, Learning Management System (Canvass, and many more), and other educational platforms.	4.61	Very High Level
3. that there are class breaks or health breaks (digital detox) for the physical, emotional, and mental health in an online learning modality	3.96	High Level
4. to make self-reflection, journals, and notes regarding my online learning experience.	3.67	High Level
5. that there is a constant communication of learners from the professors/faculty members related to online learning modality	4.04	High Level
6. that there is a safe online learning environment that creates space and privacy	4.14	High Level
7. that there are virtual reminders, encouraging notes, and things to ponder in an online learning modality	4.08	High Level
8. that my professor/ faculty member provides feedback related to online learning modality	3.88	High Level
9. of coping with the new and unexpected events	4.00	High Level
10. on accepting stance towards different life experiences	4.28	High Level
Overall Mean	4.09	High Level

Interpreting the area of mindfulness, as presented in Table 2, the overall mean score was 4.09, interpreted as "high level." The respondents obtained the highest mean score of 4.61 on item No. 2, which states "of the use of online modules or learning materials available on the internet such as YouTube, Google, Learning Management System (Canvass, and many more), and other educational platforms." interpreted as "very high level." Meanwhile, the lowest mean of 3.67 was on item No. 4, which states that I should make self-reflection, journals, and notes regarding my online learning experience at a "high level."

This implies that nursing students exhibit high levels of mindfulness in these areas, which may contribute to their overall resilience in the online learning environment. For example, students may have reported limited engagement in self-reflection, journals, and notes regarding their online learning experience. It is important to note that mindfulness is a positive predictor of resilience, according to Liao et al. (2022); thus, this high level of mindfulness can affect a nursing student's resilience.

In addition, self-awareness, mindfulness, and positive relationships foster resilience among individuals (Cagayan, 2021). The high levels of mindfulness reported by nursing students in this study further imply that they can adapt to the challenges posed by online learning, including the need for self-reflection, effective communication, and coping with unexpected events, as supported by the study of Masten (2016).

Table 3
Level of Resilience of Nursing Students in Online Learning Modalities on Positive Relationship

Area	Mean	Interpretation
C. Positive relationship		
<i>As a student, I.</i>		
1. maintain a harmonious relationship with others.	4.40	High Level
2. show open communication with my parents and professors.	3.64	High Level
3. show commitment and dedication to my academic studies.	4.44	High Level
4. acknowledge the support of the parents and stakeholders in the implementation of online learning modalities.	4.41	High Level
5. acknowledge feedback from my professors to improve myself.	4.40	High Level

6. interact appropriately and respectfully in dealing with others (classmates, professors, others).	4.70	Very High Level
7. listen to others, and others listen to me (classmates, professors, others).	4.44	High Level
8. feel safe expressing my queries, concerns, and feelings regarding the online learning modality.	3.65	High Level
9. can handle conflicts and issues related to online learning.	3.83	High Level
10. enjoy time spent with others in an online learning modality.	3.48	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	4.14	High Level

In building positive relationships, as shown in Table 3, the overall mean score was 4.14, interpreted as a "high level." The respondents obtained the highest mean score of 4.70 on item No. 6, which states, "interact appropriately and with respect in dealing with other people (classmates, professors, others)." interpreted as "very high level." Meanwhile, the lowest mean of 3.48 was on item No. 10, which states that enjoying time spent with others in an online learning modality is interpreted as a "moderate level."

Notably, the moderate enjoyment level in spending time with others online (Mean = 3.48) implies that some students may face challenges in fully embracing the online learning experience. This strengthens the conclusion of the study by Head et al. (2022) that nursing students have been faced with challenges to learn and develop; thus, they gain resistance to the pandemic as well.

For Suryaman et al. (2020), the pandemic identified obstacles encountered by students learning at home, such as limited interaction/socialization between and among students. Further, this affects their enjoyment of an online learning modality. This agrees with the findings of Savitsky et al. (2020), who identified anxiety among students during the COVID-19 pandemic, which affects the learning experience in an online learning modality.

Table 4
Level of Resilience of Nursing Students in Online Learning Modalities on Self-Awareness According to Age

Categories	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
A. Self-Awareness <i>As a student, I am.</i>				
1. aware of the different remote teaching modalities implemented by CHED.	4.29	High Level	4.21	High Level
2. aware of the dos and don'ts of implementing online learning modality during the pandemic.	4.60	Very High Level	4.45	High Level
3. aware of the importance of using ICT in online learning and school paperwork.	4.68	Very High Level	4.66	Very High Level
4. aware of the need for knowledge for accurate and updated learning areas and content in the learning platforms.	4.69	Very High Level	4.67	Very High Level
5. aware of the emotional components of the online learning modality.	4.41	High Level	4.34	High Level
6. aware of the importance of taking care of my physical, emotional, and mental health.	4.38	High Level	4.45	High Level
7. aware of the strengths of the online learning modality.	4.28	High Level	4.26	High Level
8. aware of the weaknesses and limitations of the online learning modality.	4.63	Very High Level	4.69	Very High Level
9. aware of my mindset to meet goals and needs and face challenges.	4.43	High Level	4.41	High Level
10. aware to maintain or sustain positive relationships in a challenging situation.	4.28	High Level	4.31	High Level
Overall Mean	4.46	High Level	4.44	High Level

The overall mean score obtained was 4.46 for the younger respondents and 4.44 for the older respondents, both at "high level." The younger respondents obtained their highest mean score of 4.69 on item No. 4, which states "aware of the need of knowledge for accurate and updated learning areas and content in the learning platforms." interpreted as "very high level," while the lowest mean score of 4.28 on item No. 7 and 10 which states "aware of maintaining or sustaining positive relationship in a challenging situation. interpreted as "high level."

For the older respondents, item No. 8, "aware of the weaknesses and limitations of the online learning modality," obtained the highest mean score of 4.69, interpreted as "very high level." In contrast, item 1, which states ". aware of the different remote teaching modalities implemented by CHED," with an overall mean score of 4.21, interpreted as "high level," obtained the lowest mean score.

The data regarding the level of resilience of nursing students in online learning modalities, particularly in self-awareness according to age, implies interesting insights that agree with various concepts discussed in the literature. The mean scores indicate that both younger and older nursing students demonstrate high levels of self-awareness in remote teaching modalities like online learning and its strengths and maintain or sustain a positive relationship in a challenging situation.

This finding is supported by the conceptual literature that emphasizes the importance of self-awareness in fostering resilience (Cagayan, 2021; Linde, 2020). Resilient individuals, as described in the literature, possess self-awareness and understand their strengths, limitations, and emotional components of challenging situations (Masten, 2016), especially during this time of COVID-19 pandemic when there is a significant shift in the study of online or e-learning and the educational system as mentioned by Balsicas et al. (2021),

Table 5
Level of Resilience of Nursing Students in Online Learning Modalities on Mindfulness According to Age

Area	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
B. Mindfulness				
V				
1. that my professor/faculty member introduces the concepts, pedagogy, technology, strategies, and instructional designs in an online learning modality	4.34	High Level	4.17	High Level
2. of online modules or learning materials, such as YouTube, Google, Learning Management System (Canvass, and many more), and other educational platforms.	4.63	Very High Level	4.59	Very High Level
3. that there are class breaks or health breaks (digital detox) for the physical, emotional, and mental health in an online learning modality	3.98	High Level	3.95	High Level
4. to make self-reflection, journals, and notes regarding my online learning experience.	3.75	High Level	3.57	High Level
5. that there is a constant communication of learners from the professors/ faculty members related to online learning modality	4.08	High Level	4.00	High Level
6. that there is a safe online learning environment that creates space and privacy	4.23	High Level	4.03	High Level
7. that there are virtual reminders, encouraging notes, and things to ponder in an online learning modality	4.21	High Level	3.90	High Level
8. that my professor/ faculty member provides feedback related to online learning modality	4.01	High Level	3.69	High Level
9. of coping with the new and unexpected events	4.04	High Level	3.95	High Level
10. on accepting stance towards different life experiences	4.28	High Level	4.28	High Level
Overall Mean	4.15	High Level	4.01	High Level

As exhibited, for the younger respondents, the overall mean score obtained was 4.15; for the older respondents, the overall mean score obtained was 4.01, both interpreted as "high level." The younger and the older respondents obtained their highest mean score of 4.63 and 4.59, respectively, on item No. 2, which states "of the use of online modules or learning materials available in the internet such as YouTube, Google, Learning Management System (Canvass, and many more), and other educational platforms." which is interpreted as "very high level," while the lowest mean score for younger and older respondents of 3.75 both on item No. 4 which states "to make self-reflection, journals, and notes to myself regarding my online learning experience interpreted as "high level."

The data presented reveals nursing students' resilience level in online learning modalities in mindfulness according to age groups, younger or older respondents with their ability to self-reflect, and journals regarding their online learning experience.

The literature affirmed the role of mindfulness in promoting resilience among students, particularly during traumatic events like the COVID-19 pandemic (Antonini et al., 2021). This finding also aligns with the notion that

resilience involves adapting and returning from challenging situations (Rizqi, 2017). The data also shows that nursing students exhibit high levels of mindfulness, as evidenced by their ability to self-reflect and engage in positive coping strategies related to their online learning experiences. This supports the idea that mindfulness practices integrated into online learning modalities may contribute to students' resilience and well-being. According to Liao et al. (2022), mindfulness positively predicts resilience.

Table 6
Level of Resilience of Nursing Students in Online Learning Modalities on Positive Relationship According to Age

Area	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
C. Positive relationships <i>As a student, I.</i>				
1. maintain a harmonious relationship with others.	4.40	High Level	4.40	High Level
2. show open communication with my parents and professors.	3.71	High Level	3.55	High Level
3. show commitment and dedication to my academic studies.	4.48	High Level	4.40	High Level
4. acknowledge the support of the parents and stakeholders in the implementation of online learning modalities.	4.43	High Level	4.38	High Level
5. acknowledge feedback from my professors to improve myself.	4.51	Very High Level	4.24	High Level
6. interact appropriately and respectfully in dealing with others (classmates, professors, others).	4.76	Very High Level	4.60	Very High Level
7. listen to others, and others listen to me (classmates, professors, others).	4.53	Very High Level	4.33	High Level
8. feel safe expressing my queries, concerns, and feelings regarding the online learning modality.	3.65	High Level	3.66	High Level
9. can handle conflicts and issues related to online learning.	3.88	High Level	3.78	High Level
10. enjoy time spent with others in an online learning modality.	3.49	Moderate Level	3.47	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	4.18	High Level	4.08	High Level

As exhibited by the younger respondents, the overall mean score obtained was 4.18; for the older respondents, the overall mean score obtained was 4.08, both interpreted as a "high level." The younger and the older respondents obtained their highest mean score of 4.76 and 4.60, respectively, on item No. 6, which states, "interact appropriately and with respect in dealing with other people (classmates, professors, others)." which is interpreted as "very high level," while the lowest mean score for younger and older respondents of 3.49 and 3.47 respectively on item No. 10 which states "Enjoy time spending with others in an online learning modality" interpreted as "moderate level."

The data presented indicates the level of resilience among nursing students in online learning modalities, segmented by age groups, younger and older respondents. When examining the positive relationship area, it implies that both younger and older students generally exhibit high levels of resilience, albeit with some variations across specific aspects.

In terms of building positive relationships, both younger and older students again exhibit moderate levels of resilience, particularly in areas of positive relationships in the aspect of enjoying time spent with others in an online learning modality. This supports Dashtestani's (2020) statement that regardless of age, nursing students are capable of maintaining harmonious relationships, showing open communication with parents and professors, and acknowledging the support of stakeholders in the implementation of online learning modalities. In addition, the moderate levels of resilience observed among both younger and older nursing student respondents are consistent with previous research highlighting the adaptive capacity of individuals in a challenging situation (Rizqi, 2017).

Table 7
Level of Resilience of Nursing Students in Online Learning Modalities on Self-Awareness According to Year Level

Categories	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
A. Self-Awareness <i>As a student, I am.</i>				

1. aware of the different remote teaching modalities implemented by CHED.	4.29	High Level	4.14	High Level
2. aware of the dos and don'ts of implementing online learning modality during the pandemic.	4.56	Very High Level	4.46	High Level
3. aware of the importance of using ICT in online learning and school paperwork.	4.64	Very High Level	4.74	Very High Level
4. aware of the need for knowledge for accurate and updated learning areas and content in the learning platforms.	4.65	Very High Level	4.77	Very High Level
5. aware of the emotional components of the online learning modality.	4.34	High Level	4.51	Very High Level
6. aware of the importance of taking care of my physical, emotional, and mental health.	4.35	High Level	4.57	Very High Level
7. aware of the strengths of the online learning modality.	4.23	High Level	4.37	High Level
8. aware of the weaknesses and limitations of the online learning modality.	4.63	Very High Level	4.71	Very High Level
9. aware of my mindset to meet goals and needs and face challenges.	4.38	High Level	4.54	Very High Level
10. aware to maintain or sustain positive relationships in a challenging situation.	4.24	High Level	4.43	High Level
Overall Mean	4.43	High Level	4.53	Very High Level

As presented for the lower-level BS Nursing students, the overall mean score is 4.43, interpreted as "high level." The overall mean score for the higher-level BS Nursing students is 4.53, interpreted as "very high level." The lower-level and the higher-level BS Nursing student respondents obtained their highest mean scores of 4.65 and 4.77, respectively, on item No. 4, which states, "aware of the need of knowledge for accurate and updated learning areas and content in the learning platforms." which is interpreted as "very high level."

Meanwhile, the lower-level BS Nursing student respondents' lowest mean score of 4.23 for item No.7 at "high level," and the higher-level BS Nursing student respondents' lowest mean score of 4.14 for item No. 1, which states "aware of the different remote teaching modalities implemented by CHED." which is also interpreted at "high level." The data presented regarding the level of resilience of nursing students in online learning modalities provides essential insights into various aspects of self-awareness among students of different year levels.

Implications of this data are significant in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, which has necessitated the shift to online learning modalities. Munir et al. (2021) and Dost et al. (2020) emphasize the increased importance of online teaching and learning due to the pandemic. The high levels of self-awareness among nursing students suggest that they are aware of the different teaching modalities and their strengths, thus adapting well to the challenges posed by online learning, demonstrating resilience in understanding and navigating various aspects of this new educational landscape for a lower and higher level of respondents.

This is also aligned with the findings of Barrett (2022), who highlights the resilience of nursing students in the face of pandemic-related challenges. Furthermore, while lower and higher-level students generally exhibit high levels of awareness regarding aspects such as online modules and other remote learning methods, the overall mean scores suggest that higher-level students have slightly higher awareness levels than lower-level students.

Table 8

Level of Resilience of Nursing Students in Online Learning Modalities on Mindfulness According to Year Level

Area	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
B. Mindfulness				
<i>As a student, I am mindful...</i>				
1. that my professor/faculty member introduces the concepts, pedagogy, technology, strategies, and instructional designs in an online learning modality	4.21	High Level	4.43	High Level
2. of online modules or learning materials, such as YouTube, Google, Learning Management System (Canvass, and many more), and other educational platforms.	4.56	Very High Level	4.74	Very High Level
3. that there are class breaks or health breaks (digital detox) for the physical, emotional, and mental health in	3.91	High Level	4.11	High Level

an online learning modality

4. to make self-reflection, journals, and notes regarding my online learning experience.	3.61	High Level	3.86	High Level
5. that there is a constant communication of learners from the professors/ faculty members related to online learning modality	3.99	High Level	4.20	High Level
6. that there is a safe online learning environment that creates space and privacy	4.11	High Level	4.26	High Level
7. that there are virtual reminders, encouraging notes, and things to ponder in an online learning modality	4.05	High Level	4.17	High Level
8. that my professor/ faculty member provides feedback related to online learning modality	3.88	High Level	3.86	High Level
9. of coping with the new and unexpected events	3.94	High Level	4.17	High Level
10. on accepting stance towards different life experiences	4.20	High Level	4.49	High Level
Overall Mean	4.05	High Level	4.23	High Level

As exhibited for the lower-level BS Nursing students, the overall mean score is 4.05, interpreted as "high level." The overall mean score for the higher-level BS Nursing students is 4.23, interpreted as "high level." The lower-level and the higher-level BS Nursing student respondents obtained their highest mean score of 4.56 and 4.74, respectively, on item No. 2, which states "of the use of online modules or learning materials available in the internet such as YouTube, Google, Learning Management System (Canvas and many more), and other educational platforms" which is interpreted as "very high level."

Meanwhile, for the lower-level BS Nursing student respondents, the lowest mean score was 3.61 for item No.4 at "high level," which states that. "to make self-reflection, journals, and notes to me regarding my online learning experience." For the higher-level BS Nursing student respondents, the lowest mean score was 3.86 for items No. 4 and 8, which state "to make self-reflection, journals, and notes to me regarding my online learning experience" and "that my professor or faculty member provides feedback related to online learning modality" which is also interpreted at "high level."

The data presented illustrates the level of resilience among nursing students in online learning modalities, explicitly focusing on the areas of mindfulness stratified by year level. The data consistently show high mean scores for higher- and lower-level nursing student respondents, indicating a generally positive perception of the support, interaction, and feedback professors and faculty members provided to facilitate online learning. This finding is supported by previous literature emphasizing the importance of strong interpersonal relationships in fostering student resilience (Cagayan, 2021; Lee et al., 2020).

Furthermore, the data implies that students perceive a high level of support for making self-reflections regarding the online learning experience. This is crucial, as research has supported the role of self-care in promoting resilience and mitigating the adverse effects of stress for both lower and higher-level respondents. (American Psychological Association, 2020; Adkins-Jackson et al., 2019).

Table 9

Level of Resilience of Nursing Students in Online Learning Modalities on Positive Relationship According to Year Level

Area	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
C. Positive relationship				
<i>As a student, I.</i>				
1. maintain a harmonious relationship with others.	4.36	High Level	4.51	Very High Level
2. show open communication with my parents and professors.	3.72	High Level	3.43	Moderate Level
3. show commitment and dedication to my academic studies.	4.40	High Level	4.57	Very High Level
4. acknowledge the support of the parents and stakeholders in the implementation of online learning modalities.	4.41	High Level	4.40	High Level
5. acknowledge feedback from my professors to improve myself.	4.39	High Level	4.43	High Level

6. interact appropriately and respectfully in dealing with others (classmates, professors, others).	4.71	Very High Level	4.66	Very High Level
7. listen to others, and others listen to me (classmates, professors, others).	4.44	High Level	4.46	High Level
8. feel safe expressing my queries, concerns, and feelings regarding the online learning modality.	3.71	High Level	3.49	Moderate Level
9. can handle conflicts and issues related to online learning.	3.86	High Level	3.74	High Level
10. enjoy time spent with others in an online learning modality.	3.50	High Level	3.40	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	4.15	High Level	4.11	High Level

As exhibited for the lower-level BS Nursing students, the overall mean score is 4.15, interpreted as "high level." The overall mean score for the higher-level BS Nursing students is 4.11, interpreted as "high level." The lower-level and the higher-level BS Nursing student respondents obtained their highest mean score of 4.71 and 4.66, respectively, on item No. 6, which states interact appropriately and with respect in dealing with other people (classmates, professors, others)." which is interpreted as "very high level."

Meanwhile, for the lower-level BS Nursing student respondents, the lowest mean score was 3.5 for item No.10 at "high level," which states that. "Enjoy time spent with others in an online learning modality." For the higher-level BS Nursing student respondents, the lowest mean score was 3.4 for item No. 10, which states, "Enjoy time spent with others in an online learning modality." which is interpreted as a "moderate level."

In examining the implications of this data, it is essential to consider the broader context provided by the literature. The positive relationship aspect of resilience among nursing students is evident in the data, with high/moderate levels reported across various indicators such as maintaining harmonious relationships and respect in dealing with others. This is aligned with the findings of Cagayan (2021), who highlighted the importance of strong interpersonal relationships and mindfulness in fostering student resilience. The high levels of positive relationships observed in the data suggest that nursing students effectively navigate the challenges of online learning by maintaining supportive connections with peers, professors, and family members (Table 9).

This finding also supports that nursing students, both lower-level and higher-level respondents, are effectively navigating the challenges posed by the shift to online learning modality, demonstrating resilience in positive relationships and effective communication relevant to the importance of social support in fostering resilience among nursing students in dealing with others (Walsh, 2016). It also strengthens the observation of Suryaman et al. (2020) into how learning occurred during the pandemic in which they identified that students encountered many obstacles in a home learning environment, such as lack of mastery of technology, high internet cost, and limited interaction/socialization between and among students.

Table 10

Level of Resilience of Nursing Students in Online Learning Modalities on Self-Awareness According to Average Family Monthly Income

Categories	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
A. Self-Awareness <i>As a student, I am.</i>				
1. aware of the different remote teaching modalities implemented by CHED.	4.24	High Level	4.29	High Level
2. aware of the dos and don'ts of implementing online learning modality during the pandemic.	4.48	High Level	4.63	Very High Level
3. aware of the importance of using ICT in online learning and school paperwork.	4.66	Very High Level	4.67	Very High Level
4. aware of the need for knowledge for accurate and updated learning areas and content in the learning platforms.	4.64	Very High Level	4.76	Very High Level
5. aware of the emotional components of the online learning modality.	4.36	High Level	4.43	High Level
6. aware of the importance of taking care of my physical, emotional, and mental health.	4.45	High Level	4.33	High Level

7. aware of the strengths of the online learning modality.	4.19	High Level	4.41	High Level
8. aware of the weaknesses and limitations of the online learning modality.	4.60	Very High Level	4.76	Very High Level
9. aware of my mindset to meet goals and needs and face challenges.	4.37	High Level	4.51	Very High Level
10. aware to maintain or sustain positive relationships in a challenging situation.	4.22	High Level	4.41	High Level
Overall Mean	4.42	High Level	4.52	Very High Level

As shown, for the lower average family monthly income, the overall mean score is 4.42, interpreted as "high level." For the higher average family monthly income, the overall mean score is 4.52, interpreted as "very high level." The lower average family monthly income obtained their highest mean score of 4.66 for item 3, which states "aware of the importance of the skill in the use of ICT in online learning and school paper works." For the higher average family monthly income, the highest mean score is 4.76 for items No. 4 and 8, which states "aware of the need of knowledge for accurate and updated learning areas and content in the learning platforms." and "aware of the weaknesses and limitations of the online learning modality" which is interpreted as "very high level."

On the other side, the lower average family monthly income obtained their lowest mean score of 4.19 for item No. 7, which states "aware of the strengths of the online learning modality," which is interpreted as a high level, for the higher average family monthly income, the lowest mean score of 4.29 for item No. 1 which states aware of the different remote teaching modalities implemented by CHED" which is interpreted as "high level." The data presented regarding nursing students' resilience level in online learning modalities, categorized by self-awareness, provides valuable insights into the implications of the student's experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic, particularly in online learning modalities. As stated by Suryaman et al. (2020), students are aware of home learning challenges during the pandemic, such as lack of mastery of technology, high internet costs, and limited interaction/socialization between and among students.

Regarding self-awareness and adaptability, the study indicates that nursing students, regardless of their family income level, exhibit a high self-awareness level across various online learning modalities. For higher income, the awareness of the different remote teaching modalities in which online learning modality is an example, while for lower-income, the strengths of online learning modality. This finding aligns with the notion that resilience involves adapting and returning from challenging situations (Rizqi, 2017). Despite the abrupt shift to online learning, students demonstrate awareness of different teaching modalities implemented by CHED for higher-income family respondents and its strengths for lower-income family respondents. This suggests that students have actively engaged in self-reflection and have recognized the need to adapt to the new learning environment, which is crucial for resilience (McIntosh & Shaw, 2017).

Table 11

Level of Resilience of Nursing Students in Online Learning Modalities on Mindfulness According to Average Family Monthly Income

Area	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
B. Mindfulness				
<i>As a student, I am mindful...</i>				
1. that my professor/faculty member introduces the concepts, pedagogy, technology, strategies, and instructional designs in an online learning modality	4.29	High Level	4.22	High Level
2. of online modules or learning materials, such as YouTube, Google, Learning Management System (Canvass, and many more), and other educational platforms.	4.57	Very High Level	4.67	Very High Level
3. that there are class breaks or health breaks (digital detox) for the physical, emotional, and mental health in an online learning modality	3.99	High Level	3.92	High Level
4. to make self-reflection, journals, and notes regarding my online learning experience.	3.65	High Level	3.71	High Level
5. that there is a constant communication of learners from the professors/ faculty members related to online learning modality	3.96	High Level	4.20	High Level

6. that there is a safe online learning environment that creates space and privacy	4.08	High Level	4.27	High Level
7. that there are virtual reminders, encouraging notes, and things to ponder in an online learning modality	4.00	High Level	4.22	High Level
8. that my professor/ faculty member provides feedback related to online learning modality	3.82	High Level	3.98	High Level
9. of coping with the new and unexpected events	3.99	High Level	4.02	High Level
10. on accepting stance towards different life experiences	4.33	High Level	4.18	High Level
Overall Mean	4.07	High Level	4.14	High Level

As shown for the lower average family monthly income, the overall mean score is 4.07, interpreted as "high level." For the higher average family monthly income, the overall mean score is 4.14, also interpreted as "high level." The lower and higher average family monthly income obtained their highest mean score of 4.57 and 4.67, respectively. For item no. 2, which states "of the use of online modules or learning materials available in the internet such as YouTube, Google, Learning Management System (Canvas and many more), and other educational platforms." This is interpreted as "very high level."

On the other side, both the lower and higher average family monthly income obtained their lowest mean score of 3.65 and 3.71, respectively, for item No. 4, which states, "to make self-reflection, journals, and notes to myself regarding my online learning experience," which is interpreted as "high level." The data presented regarding the resilience of nursing students in online learning modalities, categorized by average family monthly income, provides valuable insights into the factors influencing students' ability to adapt and thrive in the face of challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic. The literature surrounding resilience, particularly in the context of higher education and nursing students, supports the implications of these findings. The higher and lower average family monthly income is mindful of their online learning experience.

According to the study conducted by Munir et al. (2021), the COVID-19 pandemic has necessitated a shift to online learning, impacting students globally. The resilience of nursing students becomes particularly relevant in this context, as they face unique challenges in adapting to virtual learning environments (Barrett, 2022), which makes them mindful of their online learning experience. The data from Table 13 reveals varying levels of resilience among students from different socio-economic backgrounds with lower or higher monthly family income, with implications for their ability to cope with the demands of online education, which can be expressed through self-reflection, journals, and notes. The literature also supports the significance of mindfulness practices in enhancing resilience, particularly during traumatic events like the COVID-19 pandemic (Antonini et al., 2021), such as self-reflection, journals, and notes.

Table 12

Level of Resilience of Nursing Students in Online Learning Modalities on Positive Relationship According to Average Family Monthly Income

Area	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
C. Positive relationship				
<i>As a student, I.</i>				
1. maintain a harmonious relationship with others.	4.43	High Level	4.35	High Level
2. show open communication with my parents and professors.	3.65	High Level	3.63	High Level
3. show commitment and dedication to my academic studies.	4.47	High Level	4.39	High Level
4. acknowledge the support of the parents and stakeholders in the implementation of online learning modalities.	4.31	High Level	4.57	Very High Level
5. acknowledge feedback from my professors to improve myself.	4.37	High Level	4.45	High Level
6. interact appropriately and respectfully in dealing with others (classmates, professors, others).	4.66	Very High Level	4.76	Very High Level

7. listen to others, and others listen to me (classmates, professors, others).	4.37	High Level	4.57	Very High Level
8. feel safe expressing my queries, concerns, and feelings regarding the online learning modality.	3.57	High Level	3.80	High Level
9. can handle conflicts and issues related to online learning.	3.84	High Level	3.82	High Level
10. enjoy time spent with others in an online learning modality.	3.42	Moderate Level	3.59	High Level
Overall Mean	4.11	High Level	4.19	High Level

The lower average family income obtained an overall mean score of 4.11, and the higher average family income got 4.19, both at high levels. Both the lower and higher average family monthly income obtained their highest mean score of 4.66 and 4.76, respectively, for item No. 6, which states, "interact appropriately and with respect in dealing with other people (classmates, professors, others)," which is interpreted as "very high level."

Meanwhile, both the lower and higher average family monthly income obtained their lowest mean score of 3.42 (moderate level) and 3.59 (high level), respectively, for item No. 10, which states, "Enjoy time spent with others in an online learning modality. The data regarding the level of resilience of nursing students in online learning modalities, particularly concerning the average family monthly income, implies several noteworthy trends. In the transition of lessons, students from lower and higher income backgrounds demonstrate a moderate to high level of resilience across various aspects, such as maintaining harmonious relationships, showing commitment to academic studies, acknowledging support from parents and stakeholders, and interacting appropriately with others.

However, students from higher income backgrounds tend to acknowledge feedback from professors more positively and feel safer expressing concerns related to online learning. In addition, regarding financial influence on resilience, there is a slight variation in mean scores between students from lower and higher-income families. This challenges the notion that financial constraints may hinder students' ability to cope with the challenges of online learning, as affirmed by Clemen et al. (2021), can affect their interpersonal relationship with others during an online class, which is identified by Suryaman et al. (2020) such as lack of mastery of technology, high internet cost, and limited interaction/socialization between and among students.

Table 13

Difference in the Level of Resilience of Nursing Students in Online Learning Modalities on Self-Awareness when grouped and compared according to the abovementioned variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	80	70.64	2228.500	0.692		Not Significant
	Older	58	67.92				
Year Level	Lower	103	67.27	1573.000	0.260	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	35	76.06				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	89	66.84	1944.000	0.291		Not Significant
	Higher	49	74.33				

As presented on the variable age, the computed U is 2228.5 with a p-value of 0.692, which is greater than the 0.05 significance level, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of resilience of nursing students in online learning modality on self-awareness when grouped and compared according to age" is accepted.

In terms of variable year level, the computed U is 1573 with a p-value of 0.260, which is greater than 0.05 significance level, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of resilience of nursing students in online learning modality on self-awareness" when grouped and compared according to year level is accepted.

Concerning the average family monthly income variable, the computed U is 1944 with a p-value of 0.291, which is more significant than the 0.05 significance level and, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis that "there is no significant difference in the level of resilience of nursing students in online learning modality on self-awareness when grouped and compared according to average family monthly income" is accepted.

In conclusion, while the data did not reveal significant differences in nursing students' resilience level in online learning modality based on age, year level, or average family monthly income, it highlights the need for targeted interventions to support students' resilience regardless of demographic factors. By integrating evidence-based resilience-building strategies into nursing education programs and fostering supportive learning environments, educators can empower students to thrive amidst the challenges of online learning, ultimately enhancing their overall well-being and academic success (Savitsky et al., 2020; Klainin-Yobas et al., 2021). Additionally, future research should continue to explore the complex interplay between individual characteristics and environmental factors in shaping students' resilience in online learning contexts, informing the development of tailored interventions to support their diverse needs.

Table 14

Difference in the Level of Resilience of Nursing Students in Online Learning Modalities on Mindfulness when grouped and compared according to the abovementioned variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	80	72.71	2063.000	0.267		Not Significant
	Older	58	65.07				
Year Level	Lower	103	66.75	1519.500	0.165	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	35	77.59				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	89	68.26	2070.000	0.622		Not Significant
	Higher	49	71.76				

As shown on the variable age, the computed U is 2053 with a *p*-value of 0.267, more significant than the 0.05 level of significance, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of resilience of nursing students in online learning modality on mindfulness when grouped and compared according to age" is accepted.

In terms of variable year level, the computed U is 1519 with a *p*-value of 0.165, which is greater than the 0.05 significance level, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of resilience of nursing students in online learning modality on mindfulness" when grouped and compared according to year level is accepted.

Regarding the average family monthly income variable, the computed U is 2070 with a *p*-value of 0.622, more significant than the 0.05 significance level, thus interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis that states nursing students' resilience level in online learning modality on mindfulness, when grouped and compared according to average family monthly income," is accepted.

The data in Table 14 illustrates the difference in resilience among nursing students in online learning modalities concerning mindfulness when grouped and compared according to various variables such as age, year level, and average family monthly income. Upon analyzing the data, it is evident that there are no significant differences in resilience levels based on age, year level, or average family monthly income, as indicated by the non-significant *p*-values for these variables.

In conclusion, the findings of this study have important implications for nursing education and student support services, particularly in the context of online learning modalities. By understanding the factors contributing to resilience among nursing students, educators and administrators can develop targeted interventions to support students' well-being and academic success in the face of challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic and beyond.

Table 15

Difference in the Level of Resilience of Nursing Students in Online Learning Modalities on Positive Relationships when grouped and compared according to the abovementioned variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	80	72.81	2055.000	0.252		Not Significant
	Older	58	64.93				
Year Level	Lower	103	70.13	1737.500	0.750	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	35	67.64				

	Lower	89	68.30			
Average Family Monthly Income	Higher	49	71.67	2074.000	0.635	Not Significant

As shown on the variable age, the computed U is 2055 with a p -value of 0.252, which is more significant than the 0.05 level of significance, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of resilience of nursing students in online learning modality on a positive relationship when grouped and compared according to age" is accepted.

In terms of variable year level, the computed U is 1737.5 with a p -value of 0.750, which is more significant than the 0.05 level of significance, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of resilience of nursing students in online learning modality on a positive relationship" when grouped and compared according to year level is accepted.

Regarding the variable, average family monthly income, the computed U is 2074 with a p -value of 0.635, which is more significant than the 0.05 significance level, thus interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis that states nursing students' resilience level in online learning modality on positive relationships when grouped and compared according to average family monthly income" is accepted.

The data presented regarding the difference in the level of resilience of nursing students in online learning modalities provides valuable insights into various aspects of resilience and its implications in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic. When examining the variables of age, year level, and average family monthly income, the Mann-Whitney U test revealed no significant differences in resilience levels among younger and older students, those in lower and higher year levels, and those with lower and higher average family monthly incomes. However, when focusing on building positive relationships, it becomes evident that there are noteworthy distinctions in resilience levels between younger and older students.

In conclusion, the data presented shed light on the resilience levels of nursing students in online learning modalities, particularly in building positive relationships. These findings underscore the importance of fostering positive relationships and support networks within the online learning environment to enhance students' resilience amid the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic. By incorporating evidence-based resilience-building strategies, educational institutions can better support nursing students' well-being and academic success in the evolving landscape of higher education.

Conclusions

Based on the analyzed and interpreted data presented in this study, there was a high level of self-awareness regarding the level of resilience of nursing students in the online learning modality, therefore, concluded that students must be informed or oriented to CHED's different remote teaching modalities. Also, nursing students exhibited a high level of mindfulness in the online learning modality and concluded that nursing students can make self-reflections, journals, and notes to themselves regarding their online learning experience to increase mindfulness. Further, nursing students exhibited a high level of positive relationship in the online learning modality and concluded that students need extra time to spend with others in an online learning modality. Results of the study show the level of students' resiliency in self-awareness, mindfulness, and positive relationships did not vary even though they were grouped and compared according to age, year level, and highest educational attainment. However, it was also concluded that nursing students' resiliency level in self-awareness may be influenced by their year level and average family monthly income. In conclusion, the findings of this study shed light on the resilience levels of nursing students in online learning modality across various demographic factors and specific areas of online learning experiences.

Moving forward, the study highlights the need for tailored interventions and support mechanisms to enhance resilience among nursing students, particularly in the context of online learning amid the COVID-19 pandemic. Educators and policymakers can utilize these insights to develop targeted strategies to support student well-being and academic success. By addressing the nuanced aspects of resilience within online learning environments, institutions can contribute to creating a more resilient and adaptive nursing workforce capable of navigating the challenges of contemporary healthcare education.

This study's finding calls for: 1) in psychology education, it is recommended to integrate resilience-building strategies into the curriculum to equip students with the necessary skills to thrive in challenging academic environments. This can include incorporating mindfulness practices, stress management techniques, and interpersonal skills development into coursework to enhance students' ability to cope with adversity and stress; 2)

in psychological practice, practitioners must incorporate evidence-based resilience interventions into their clinical work to support clients in overcoming adversity and achieving positive outcomes. This entails evaluating clients' strengths and resilience factors, like social support networks, coping strategies, and adaptive thinking patterns, and then adapting interventions to suit these assessments; 3) in psychological institutions, the administration must prioritize the well-being of students, faculty, and staff by implementing thorough wellness programs and support services. This includes offering access to mental health resources, counseling services, and peer support networks to meet the diverse needs of the institution's members; and 4) in psychological research, it is crucial to continue exploring the factors contributing to resilience across diverse populations and contexts to inform evidence-based interventions and practices. This involves conducting longitudinal studies to examine the long-term effects of resilience interventions and identify protective factors that promote resilience over time.

Acknowledgment

The researcher would like to express heartfelt, genuine thanks and appreciation to the following persons who willingly gave their help and valuable time in converting this research work to become publishable. To Dr. Ma Leni C. Francisco, his adviser, whose continuous guidance and criticism helped the researcher to develop critical thinking as well as pushed this researcher in polishing this work. To all panel members and moderator, for their constructive criticism, scholarly insights and valuable suggestions that greatly enhanced the quality of this output. To Audi Cristiano and Twinkle, who has been a profound source of inspiration of the researcher. And, to Daddy, Mommy, Glady and Inyaw, who have always been a constant source of strength and encouragement, without them this study could never have completed. Everyone, THANK YOU.

References

- Adkins-Jackson, P. B., Turner-Musa, J., & Chester, C. (2019). The path to better health for black women: Predicting self-care and exploring its mediating effects on stress and health. *INQUIRY: The Journal of Health Care Organization, Provision, and Financing*, p. 56, 0046958019870968.
- American Psychological Association. (2020, February 1). *Building your resilience*. <https://www.apa.org/topics/resilience/building-your-resilience>
- Antonini Philippe R, Schwab L and Biasutti M (2021). Effects of Physical Activity and Mindfulness on Resilience and Depression During the First Wave of COVID-19 Pandemic. *Front. Psychol.* 12:700742. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2021.70074
- Atkins, E., & Muscat-Inglott, M. (2023). The relationship between mindfulness and resilience in Maltese undergraduates: a study of affective well-being as a potential mediator.
- Authority, P. S. (2018). and 2015 Family Income and Expenditure Survey.
- Barrett D Impact of COVID-19 on nursing students: What does the evidence tell us? *Evidence-Based Nursing* 2022;25:37-38.
- Cagayan, C. (2021). *TEACHERS' RESILIENCY ON REMOTE TEACHING MODALITIES: BASIS FOR PSYCHOSOCIAL WELLNESS PLAN* [Master's thesis, STI WEST NEGROS UNIVERSITY].
- Clemen I, Ali H, Abdulmadid A, Jabbar J, *Education during COVID-19 Era: Readiness of Students in a Less-Economically Developed Country for E-Learning* Iligan Medical Center College Journal of Science (2021)
- Dashtestani, R. (2020). Online courses in the higher education system of Iran: A stakeholder-based investigation of percale-service teachers' acceptance, learning achievement, and satisfaction. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 21(4), 117-142. <https://doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v21i4.4873>
- Engada, J. D., & Maguate, G. (2023). PROJECT LEARNDEMIC (Learning Assessment and Reading Development through Enhanced Modified Intervention and Collaboration). *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management (IJSRM)*, 11(09), 31-41.
- GARMEZY, N. (1991a). Resilience in children's adaptation to negative life events and stressed environments. *Pediatric Annals*, pp. 20, 459-460, 463-466.
- GARMEZY, N. (1991b). Resiliency and vulnerability to adverse developmental outcomes associated with poverty. *The American Behavioral Scientist*, pp. 34, 416.
- Head ML, Acosta S, Bickford EG, Leatherland MA. Impact of COVID-19 on Undergraduate Nursing Education: Student Perspectives. *Acad Med.* 2022 Mar 1;97(3S):S49-S54. Doi: 10.1097/ACM.0000000000004530. PMID: 34789659; PMCID: PMC8855759.
- Head, Morgan L. RN1; Acosta, Samantha RN2; Bickford, Emma G. RN3; Leatherland, Malia A. RN4. Impact of COVID-19 on Undergraduate Nursing Education: Student Perspectives. *Academic Medicine* 97(3S):p S49-S54, March 2022. | DOI: 10.1097/ACM.0000000000004530
- Jayme, R., & Maguate, G. (2023). Issues and Concerns of Teachers towards Modular Distance Learning Approach. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management (IJSRM)*, 11(08), 2848-2857.

- Joaquin, J. J., Biana, H. T., & Dacela, M. A. (2020). The Philippine Higher Education Sector in the Time of COVID-19. *Frontiers in Education*, 5. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2020.576371>
- Klainin-Yobas, P., Vongsirimas, N., Ramirez, D.Q. et al. Evaluating the relationships among stress, resilience and psychological well-being among young adults: a structural equation modeling approach. *BMC Nurs* 20, 119 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-021-00645-9>
- Lee, T. S. H., Wu, Y. J., Chao, E., Chang, C. W., Hwang, K. S., & Wu, W. C. (2021). Resilience as a mediator of interpersonal relationships and depressive symptoms amongst 10th to 12th grade students. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 278, 107-113.
- Liao, J., Sun, X., Mai, X., Du, Y., & Li, F. (2022). Mindfulness and mental health in medical staff in the COVID-19 period: Mediating role of perceived social support and sense of security. *Journal of Psychology in Africa*, 32(5), 447-453.
- Masha'al, D., Rababa, M., & Shahrour, G. (2020). Distance learning-related stress among undergraduate nursing students during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Nursing Education*, 59(12), 666-674. <https://doi.org/10.3928/01484834-20201118-03>
- Masten, A. S. (2016). Promoting resilience in development: A general framework for systems of care. In *Promoting Resilience in Child Welfare*. Ottawa: University of Ottawa Press.
- Masten, A.S., Motti-Stefanidi, F. Multisystem Resilience for Children and Youth in Disaster: Reflections in the Context of COVID-19. *ADV RES SCI* 1, 95-106 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42844-020-00010-w>
- Mcintosh, E. & Shaw, J. (2017). Student Resilience: Exploring the Positive Case for Resilience.
- Miranda, J. O., & Cruz, R. N. C. (2020). Resilience mediates the relationship between optimism and well-being among Filipino university students. *Current Psychology*, 1-10.
- Rizqi, A. (2017). Stress and Resilience among EFL Teachers: An Interview Study of an Indonesian Junior High School Teacher. *TEFLIN Journal*.
- Salanga, I., Pascual-Dormido, Y., Villanueva, M., & Maguate, G. (2023). Emergency Response in a Highly-Urbanized City: Basis for a Capability Building Plan. *Excellencia: International Multi-disciplinary Journal of Education* (2994-9521), 1(6), 207-233.
- Savitsky B, Findling Y, Erel A, Hendel T. Anxiety and coping strategies among nursing students during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Nurse Educ Pract*. 2020 Jul;46:102809. doi: 10.1016/j.nepr.2020.102809. Epub 2020 Jun 2. PMID: 32679465; PMCID: PMC7264940.
- Staneva, A., Carmignani, F., & Rohde, N. (2022). Personality, gender, and age resilience to the mental health effects of COVID-19. *Social science & medicine*, 301, 114884.
- Suryaman, M., Cahyono, Y., Muliansyah, D., Bustani, O., Suryani, P., Fahlevi, M., & Munthe, A. P. (2020). COVID-19 Pandemic and Home Online Learning System: Does it Affect the Quality of Pharmacy School Learning? *Systematic Reviews in Pharmacy*, 11, 524-530.
- Tanji, F., Nanbu, H., Ono, M., Abe, N., & Nitta, J. (2021). The association between resilience and academic performance among nursing students: a cross-sectional study in Japan. *Journal of Rural Medicine*, 16(4), 206-213.
- Walsh, F. (2016). Foundations of a family resilience approach. In *Strengthening family resilience* (3rd ed.). (pp. 3-21). New York: Guilford.
- Zolotov, Y., Reznik, A., Bender, S., & Isralowitz, R. (2020). COVID-19 fear, mental health, and substance use among Israeli university students. *International Journal of Mental Health and Addiction*, 1-7. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11469-020-00351-8>